

PROSPECT OF USING THE EXPERIENCE OF GREAT BRITAIN FOR SUCCESSFUL INTEGRATION OF E-LEARNING INTO THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

The research highlights the study of normative and organizational aspects of E-learning in Ukrainian and British system of Higher Education. A comparative analysis of this innovative phenomenon in both countries reveals the priorities in E-learning strategies. It was found out that the aim of Ukrainian E-learning system is the direction to the modernization of the initial process organization by means of the implementation of remote learning technologies that is a little differs from British one which is directed mainly to the improving of possibilities of satisfying the needs of the labor market for the additional possibilities of E-learning; making investments to the promotion of new ICT in education by a number of innovative programs related to it; improving of the inclusive nature of public education. The results of research enable to outline the possibilities of creative use of elements of experience of Great Britain in the investigated field in Ukraine.

Keywords: normative aspects, E-learning strategies, individualization of education, global information resources, innovation system

An emergent shift of the majority of educational institutions in Ukraine to distance learning in the virtual academic environment occurred due to the Russian invasion. The rapid use of ICT in the system of higher education, which includes the use of the latest distance learning methods, the adaptation of relevant abilities, skills and competencies raised the issue of a comprehensive study of key aspects of E-learning development.

Therefore, the necessity to introduce elements of electronic learning into the national education system is mentioned in the "National Strategy for the Development of Education in Ukraine". Its key aspects are the following:

1) formation and implementation of an informational and educational environment in the system of higher and postgraduate education; 2) development of individual modular training programs of different levels of complexity depending on specific needs; 3) creation of an information system that will support the educational process aimed at the implementation of its key functions (providing training courses, socialization, internal control over the implementation of educational standards, etc.); 4) supply of the educational process by means of information and communication technologies, as well as access of educational institutions to global information resources; 5) creation of a network of electronic libraries at all levels of education, as well as electronic textbooks and educational encyclopedias; 6) creation of a inclusive distance learning system; 7) creation of a system of information and analytical support in terms of management of educational institutions, information and technological support for education monitoring [1].

Therefore, according to the "National Strategy for the Development of Education in Ukraine" the aim of E-learning is to enable people to obtain education and professional qualifications according to the constitutional law [2].

The realization of main principles of E-Learning fulfill a number of state institutions and organizations which deal with the issue of organization and implementation of E-learning in Ukraine, in particular the Department of Higher Education of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine; Ukrainian Institute of Information Technologies and Teaching Aids; Institute for Modernization of Education Content; Institute of Educational Analytics of the Ministry of Education and Culture; Coordination Council for the Development of Distance Learning at the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine; the commission under the Coordination Council for different areas of ensuring the development of the distance learning system, the main, regional, basic and local centers of the distance learning system, which perform certain functions.

The latter are represented by higher educational institutions.

The key functions of the activity of Ukrainian higher educational institutions are the following: to ensure approval and introduction of the latest methods and technologies of E-learning into the educational process; to ensure development of distance courses, distance learning of certified distance courses, participation in international cooperation in terms of distance learning [3].

Compared to the Ukrainian system of E-learning the government of Great Britain is interested in the popularization of higher education, so it provides appropriate financial assistance to higher education institutions and students. Therefore, according to one of principal document of the country «Higher Education Act 2004» (Higher Education Act 2004) the priorities of the UK government's e-strategy include the following: 1) creation of a comprehensive online information service for all citizens (providing comprehensive information and services to students and their parents, as well as the possibility of their optimized cooperation with the administration of the educational institution); 2) providing the

integrated online individual support to students (stimulating the development of strategies for joint assistance to students in education); 3) encouraging educational institutions to transform the learning and teaching process in accordance with the needs of the labor market (taking into account and meeting the needs of the labor market regarding the quality of electronic skills for successful employment); 4) development of requirements to ensure high quality professional training and recommendations for support of practitioners (organization of online training courses for teachers); 5) providing recommendations to the administrations of educational institutions regarding the development of organizational potential in the field of ICT (supporting educational institutions in the use of ICT, as well as managing the process of using them in education, creating a national

advisory center on online learning, providing support to educational institutions that offer remote electronic teaching); 7) development of the general digital infrastructure to support transformations and reforms (testing of the national modern Internet network to support the future research and educational activities of higher education institutions).

Taking into account these advantages, the UK Government developed a program for improving the quality of education due to the digital technologies and outlined it in the document "National Framework of Professional Standards"(NFPS) [6]. The implementation of the goals of the NFPS in universities takes place in accordance with certain directions, organizational approaches and professional values of higher education institutions (see Table 1)

Table 1.
Implementation of the goals of the "National Framework of Professional Standards" of Great Britain

Areas of activity of the university	Organization of the learning process	Professional values
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - development and planning of educational programs; - support of students' studies; - assessment and provision of feedback to students; - development of effective learning environments; - integration of scientific research and education; - assessment of educational activities and lifelong professional development of teaching staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - use of teaching and learning methods that correspond to a certain subject area and level of the academic program; - use of innovative learning technologies; - introduction of appropriate methods of assessment of training effectiveness; - research based on the results of the process of improving the quality of teachers' professional practice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respect for students; - the inclusion of the results of relevant scientific research into educational programs; - intention to the development of educational communities; - encouraging the teaching staff to innovative participation in the educational process; - constant self-assessment of professional development by teaching staff

The infrastructure of the British National Innovation System is represented by universities, research institutions and public sector of research institutions. Universities have a significant impact on the country's economy, as they provide the process of commercialization of new knowledge, professional training and consulting services.

Among the key functions of innovative activity of universities are the following: support of scientific research; introduction of innovations in education and research fields; development of the creative potential of cohorts of scientists, teachers and students; inventing new forms of solving scientific and technical issues.

Findings. Thus, the use of a comparative analysis enabled the revealing that according to E-learning in Great Britain, the priority is given to the problem of ensuring the availability of higher education for all those who want it, encouraging higher education institutions to be flexible towards the respond to the demands of the labor market, promoting the development of organizational and technological innovations in education, encouraging higher education institutions to develop E-learning resources.

Taking into account the process of modernization of the Ukrainian higher education system, we consider it necessary to use the progressive experience of Great Britain in terms of organization of education in E-learning system of Ukraine.

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